

THE CONCEPT OF GREEN ECONOMY, ITS ESSENCE, AND PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *The article broadly covers the concept of green economy, its causes and significance. It also studies the views of economists on green economy, analyzes their approaches and definitions. It highlights that the main goal of green economy is to ensure efficient use of resources by coordinating economic growth, environmental sustainability, and social justice.*

Keywords: *resource conservation, fairness, prosperity, environmental sustainability, green economy, natural resources.*

Introduction

In the 21st century, alongside global economic development, countries around the world are also facing environmental challenges. Depending on each nation's specific economic conditions, certain ecological issues arise within their respective territories, manifesting at varying scales. Today, almost all countries encounter environmental problems, which are further aggravated by factors such as global climate change, air and water pollution, waste management difficulties, and the scarcity of natural resources. These very factors and the need for their effective future management have led to the emergence of the concept of the green economy. The ongoing global downturn has highlighted the structural shortcomings of current economic models, necessitating greater attention to sustainable approaches. Consequently, many countries are carefully examining broader concepts of the 'Green economy', which aim to foster both sustainability and economic growth.

The term 'Green economy' can be traced in the academic community to David Pearce's ideas presented in his book *Blueprint for a Green Economy*. According to the core concept outlined therein, due to the existing pricing system, the allocation of resources in the economy occurs at the expense of environmental degradation. Environmental assets and services are considered as production resources; as a result, some key sectors are overvalued while others are undervalued, leading to inefficient use of natural resources and causing environmental degradation. Furthermore, payments for environmental pollution often remain uncollected from the responsible parties, thereby imposing the burden on society [1].

Literature analysis and methodology

There are several relevancies of Transitioning to a Green Economy:

Firstly, at present, billions of people are not only exploiting natural resources but also using them inefficiently. As countries recover from the global economic crisis, the gap between the wealthy and the poor continues to widen.

Secondly, if we continue to allow such wastefulness, by 2050 nearly four billion people will reside in regions severely affected by water scarcity.

Thirdly, inefficient use of resources will leave more than eighty percent of the population in several countries, including China and India, dependent on energy. By 2050, the majority of their energy needs will rely on fossil fuels.

Last one of reasons is greenhouse gas emissions which will remain stable in OECD countries and Russia, while in the rapidly growing BRIICS (Brazil, Russia, India, Indonesia, China, and South Africa) countries, emissions are expected to double. This will lead to a range of serious social, economic, and environmental consequences. Increased waste globally will intensify the greenhouse effect, raising Earth's surface temperatures, exacerbating freshwater shortages, and, coupled with rapid industrialization and rising energy demand, will increase BRIICS countries' reliance on coal, oil, and gas, supporting environmentally harmful industrial sectors.

Currently, the world population exceeds 8 billion. The United Nations projects that the global population will reach 9.7 billion by 2050 and 11 billion by 2100. Consequently, while the availability of resources continues to diminish, the primary challenge of the economy-meeting the ever-growing demand-expands. Correspondingly, the scope of climate-related problems worldwide continues to broaden. As a result, issues related to food security are also intensifying on a global scale.

In October 2008, the 'Green Economy Initiative' was launched by The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) to analyze investments in green sectors, support policy implementation, and ensure the stabilization of high-environmental-risk industries. The idea aims to promote economic recovery while simultaneously improving the balance of the global economy. Given the importance of this issue, both intergovernmental and civil-society-based international organizations-such as the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the World Wildlife Fund, the International Union for Conservation of Nature, and several other institutions-play a key role as proponents of the transition to new principles of economic development that can significantly influence the advancement of the green economy.

A key work defining the green economy is the book *Green Economy: Why, What and How*, published in 2010 by the United Nations in New York. Through this work, various scholars and experts have provided insights into the essence of the green economy, its significance, and its role in economic development.

Additionally, Professor Suaad Hadi Hassan Al-Taai of the University of Baghdad highlighted that one of the main objectives of the green economy is the necessity of reforming policies and regulations that obstruct its implementation [2]. American ecological economist Robert Costanza, a prominent scholar in the field of ecological economics, has conducted numerous studies on integrating economic systems with ecological systems. He defined the green economy as 'an economic model designed to ensure social well-being and ecological sustainability' [3].

Results

To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the concept of the 'Green economy', we will examine the perspectives provided by both Uzbek and foreign economic scholars.

Table 1

Opinions of Uzbek and foreign economists about the 'Green Economy'

№	Authors	Definition and conceptual discussion
1.	S.N.Khashimov a	Green economy is a future economy in a new model based on the development of production and service sectors based on new knowledge and resource-saving technologies, while preserving the ecology of our planet [4].

2.	J.Kh.Ataniyazov	Green economy is an economic model built on the basis of efficient use of resources, renewal of energy sources, reduction of waste and preservation of natural resources [5].
3.	S.E. Elmirzayev	Green economy is an economy that helps expand economic opportunities and does not contradict environmental sustainability and social well-being [6].
4.	A.V. Vakhabov	Green economy is an important criterion for achieving sustainable development [7].
5.	A.Sen	Green economy is not only a technological approach, but also an important factor in developing human potential [8].
6.	B.Richard	Green economy is an economic model that not only reduces the environmental impact of production and consumption, but also creates a good relationship between economic growth and environmental well-being [9].

In some economic sources, although the concept of the ‘Green economy’ was first applied in 1989, its content continues to be interpreted in various ways. In certain sources, the green economy is understood as the modern sectors of the economy that contribute to the improvement of a country’s natural environment. In other literature, it is examined as leading technologies and ecosystems that support nature while generating benefits. Some studies define the green economy as a new stage of development aimed at producing environmentally friendly products, with its foundation based on pure or ‘green’ technologies.

The most widely recognized and relatively comprehensive definition of the green economy was developed by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). According to UNEP, a green economy is ‘an economy that leads to improved human well-being and social equity while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities’.

Naturally, successful transition to this type of economy requires that countries adhere to specific principles of the green economy. These principles indicate how a green economy can be achieved while ensuring a balanced integration of economic, environmental, and social benefits. Below, the main principles guiding the transition to a green economy are discussed:

- ✚ Principle of Well-being. This principle is based on ensuring a peaceful and harmonious lifestyle for all people on Earth, taking into account their political, economic, and environmental conditions.
- ✚ Principle of Equity. The equity principle of the green economy aims to provide equal opportunities across all economic layers and sectors, ensuring the responsible use of ecological and economic resources while passing them on to future generations.
- ✚ Planetary Boundaries Principle. It is well-known that all natural resources on our planet are limited. Their unregulated use can disrupt ecological balance, contribute to climate change, and pose serious risks to the health of future generations. The planetary boundaries principle seeks to prevent such imbalances by financing the protection, enhancement, and restoration of biodiversity, soil, water, air, and natural systems.
- ✚ Principle of Efficiency and Sufficiency. This principle promotes the efficient use of available resources to achieve maximum outcomes while minimizing waste, thereby ensuring sustainable development.

- ✚ Principle of Good Governance. Transparency, accountability, rule of law, participation, and responsibility are crucial for every state and its citizens. Accordingly, the green economy emphasizes open and responsible governance in ecological, economic, and social matters to promote societal well-being [10].

Thus, based on these five principles, countries can develop concrete strategies to ensure the sustainable development of the green economy, use natural resources wisely, and protect the environment. These principles help maintain ecological and social balance alongside economic growth. Furthermore, they contribute significantly to reducing social inequalities among countries and alleviating global poverty, one of the world's most pressing issues.

Conclusion

A green economy is an economic model that aims to ensure environmental sustainability and seeks to reconcile economic growth with environmental protection. This model emphasizes the rational use of resources, the transition to renewable energy sources, the reduction of waste, and social equity. A green economy not only solves environmental problems, but also creates new jobs and ensures sustainable economic growth.

The following proposals can be put forward to further green and stabilize the country's economy:

Encouraging green investment - increasing investment in environmentally friendly projects by the government and the private sector.

Developing renewable energy sources - accelerating the transition to energy sources such as solar, wind, and biogas.

Strengthening legislation supporting green technologies - creating tax incentives for technologies that meet environmental standards.

Increasing environmental awareness among the population - introducing educational programs on the green economy in schools and higher education institutions.

Establishing a sustainable transport system - developing public transport, creating infrastructure for electric vehicles.

Supporting local producers - providing subsidies to producers of environmentally friendly products.

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